

A STUDY ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENSITIVITY TRAINING PROGRAM PROVIDED TO EMPLOYEES IN TATA CONSULTANCY SERVICES

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Abstract:

This paper examines the sensitivity training provided to the employees which makes them discuss openly and interpersonal skills are developed. Sensitivity training has been conducted frequently in the organization and the employees are satisfied with the quality of training which has helped to increase the overall efficiency of the organization. If sensitivity training is not conducted properly, the problems frequently faced in an organization are lack of understanding, lack of communication, and an increase in conflict. Incorporating evidence from reviews, surveys, and personal contact, this study aims to determine the impact of sensitivity training provided to employees. Based on a review of the literature on sensitivity training, the objectives and questionnaires have been framed and distributed to the employees who have attended sensitivity training for primary data collection. This study is descriptive in nature. The type of Sampling used in this study is stratified sampling using a structured questionnaire as a research instrument. The total population of the company is 120 employees of which 50 employees of various departments have responded. The same 50 respondents have been taken as a sample size for this project. The data collected were analyzed using SPSS. The findings are positive when sensitivity training is conducted. The employees agreed that the training was helpful, interactive, engaging, supportive, understanding about the issues, and satisfied with the quality of the training. Suggestions given by the trainee have been taken into consideration. Employees also agreed that they felt confident at the end of the sensitivity training.

Keywords: Quality of the training, efficiency, interpersonal growth, sustainable development, helpful, and interactive.

INTRODUCTION:

TCS provides a workforce that is diverse and global. This helps the employees to develop their personal and professional growth. TCS gives equal opportunity to all races, nationalities, religions, and ethnic origins. They give equal importance to women employees/employers. TCS is more employee-friendly in such a way that they give extended parental leave, special leadership development, and parenting workshops for working parents. TCS takes many initiatives that it helps in the growth of the career of the employees. It also provides mentoring services. Systematic leadership reviews make the company maintain its efficiency and be successful. Their first and foremost preference is safety. As safety is their first preference, they were able to reduce fatalities in road accidents, crimes, and self-harm incidents. Apart from this sensitivity training has been conducted to reduce stress, and conflict, and increase better communication skills.

Sensitivity training is where a group of people sit together and discuss the issues and problems and come up with a solution. It helps in the growth of employees. This training is done by the HR manager. It helps us to consider the life experience of other people in the workplace. This

gives a different perception. Sensitivity training teaches many things to the employees such as respect for their peers, reducing offensive behavior, and creating more hospitality for the employees. Sensitivity training makes the organization more welcoming and creates a safer workspace. This training helps in better communication, more efficiency, and positivity.

Many people come from different backgrounds to their workplace to complete the tasks and achieve the goals and objectives. These might create various problems and can lead to negative actions. During this time sensitivity training should be conducted which helps to solve a problem and it plays a vital role in the organization.

When the employees discuss sensitivity training, it helps the employees to think beyond their current perceptions. This helps in acknowledging the misunderstanding, apologizing, and supporting each other. Similar researches have been conducted by many authors (Benita, 2021; Monica, 2021; Kumar, 2020; Kumar & Shree, 2019; Monica & Supriya, 2019; Mahesh & Uma Rani, 2019; Mahesh, Gigi, & Uma Rani, 2019; Robert & Monisha, 2019; Kumar & Shree, 2018).

Sensitivity training is significant in the company to create a welcoming space and should create a safe and pleasant work environment. It should make all the employees be respected, united, and should have a mutual understanding by acknowledging their attitudes. Sensitivity training aims to ensure that all the employees are feeling safe and secure while doing their job. It helps the employee to learn and grow and be more effective. It bridges the gap between misunderstanding and proper learning where the employees will communicate through compassion and respect.

OBJECTIVES:

Primary Objective:

To study the effectiveness of sensitivity training programs provided to employees

Secondary Objective:

- 1) To study the relationship between gender and the impact of sensitivity training on the employees
- 2) To study the relationship between educational qualification and the impact of sensitivity training on the employees

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Smith. P.B (1975). Controlled studies of the outcome of sensitivity training

According to this author, it was studied that the training lasted more than 20 hrs. Out of 100 studies, 78% found a change. This is greater than it had shown in control. Out of 31 studies, 21 found a greater change. The changes that the employees had were a reduction in preconceived notions, an increase in self-actualization, and an increase in interpersonal skills. There were also modifications in organizational behavior.

Lewis, P., Dawes, A. S., & Cheney, T. (1974), Effects of sensitivity training on belief in internal control of interpersonal relationships. According to this author, this study is about the T-group experience of the employees about the locus of control. The locus of control of interpersonal relationships had 19 closed-ended questions. It had 32 males and the females were placed in 2 T-groups and 1 control group. This was conducted by both male and female co-therapist for a weekend. It was said that employees would change for internal beliefs or training.

Levenberg, S. B., & Spakes, J. W. (1975). Locus of control of reinforcement and attraction in sensitivity group settings. 5 sensitivity groups had 64 undergraduate and graduate students. It was hypothesized that an internal Sensitivity group setting would represent a stronger interpersonal attraction for fellow internals, whereas an external Sensitivity group setting would represent a greater interpersonal attraction for group members who have an exterior orientation. The findings indicate that verbalization volume was not associated with to own locus of control score but was related to attractiveness. Ss did not exhibit any preference for people who shared their locus of control orientation. Internals favored other people who shared similar locus of control orientations but did not relate to their internal orientation. Discussion is held regarding methodological issues with a locus of control studies

Casey, N. A., & Solomon, L. (1971-1972). The effect of seating arrangements on T-group interaction and sociometric choices. It provides a comprehensive assessment of the personal space literature with a focus on the psychological significance of the topic for both healthy and diseased populations. The major premise that modifications in the visual-spatial seating position have a significant impact on the network of interaction was proven by systematic observation of an 18-member T-group over 7 months. The group consisted of 17 university seniors and a professor-trainer. With time, this bond deteriorates.

Ganzarain, R. (1974-1975). A psychoanalytic study of sensitivity training. It discusses anxiety's role in expecting "miracle results" and irrational aspirations, as well as how anxiety influences participation in sensitivity training groups. The relationship between depressed separation anxiety and methods of defending against them is examined, and psychoanalytic research on psychotic anxieties is compiled. It is suggested that one of the main duties of the sensitivity training group is to help members understand occurrences that resemble psychosis and occur in the group. Consideration is given to the "now" as the focal point of several psychological theories, and the demand for a unifying conceptualization based on object relations psychoanalytic theory is investigated.

Golembiewski, Robert T. Blumberg, Arthur. Sensitivity Training and the Laboratory Approach. This focuses on descriptions of T-groups and reactions to T-groups, leadership roles, member roles, methods and goals, and results. It also talks about T-group dynamics. It suggests their flavor and texture. It analyses group development. In order to understand, it also provides theoretical frameworks

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

A research methodology is a means to describe how a researcher plans to conduct their investigation. The researcher will conduct various studies on the accuracy, and legitimate data to meet their goals, and its objectives. It includes the data gathered by the researcher, where they have gathered it, and how they will analyze the data. This study is descriptive in nature. The type of Sampling used in this study is stratified sampling using a structured questionnaire as a research instrument. The total population of the company is 120 employees of which 50 employees of various departments have responded. The same 50 respondents have been taken as a sample size for this project.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Chart 1.0: Classification of Respondece Based On Gender

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	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	21	50
Female	21	50
Total	42	100

From the above classification, it could be found that 55.1% of respondents are male employees and 44.9% of respondents are female employees

Chart 1.1: Classification of Respondents Based On Educational Qualification

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	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
SSC	3	7.1
HSC	3	7.1
UG	27	64.3
PG	9	21.4
TOTAL	42	100

Interpretation:

From the above table, it could be inferred that the majority of the respondents from UG with a percentage of 63.3%

Chart 1.2:

Interpretation:

From the above classification, it was interpreted that 77.6% of the employees agree that sensitivity training was helpful

Chart 1.3:

Interpretation:

From the above classification, it was interpreted that 63.3% of the employees agree that sensitivity training allows them to gain a picture of the impact that HR makes on them

Chart 1.4:

Sensitivity trainer supportive and understandable about the issues and the problems
49 responses

Interpretation:

From the above classification, it was interpreted that 51% of the employees agree that the sensitivity trainer was supportive and understanding about the issues

Chart 1.5:

Sensitivity training met my expectation
49 responses

Interpretation:

From the above classification, it was interpreted that 53.1% of the employees agree that the sensitivity training met their expectations.

Chart 1.6:

I felt confident and competent at the end of the training programme
49 responses

Interpretation:

From the above classification, it was interpreted that 55.1% of the employees agree that they felt confident and competent at the end of the training program.

Table 1.2: Independent Sample T-Test

	T VALUE	SIGNIFICANT VALUE
Sensitivity training helpful to me	0.330	0.164
The sensitivity training program is interactive and engaging	1.029	0.270
Sensitivity training allows me to gain a picture of the impact that HR makes on me	2.180	0.000
Sensitivity training conducted me at my own pace	0.000	0.483
A sensitivity trainer is supportive and understanding about the issues and the problems	1.611	0.001

Inference: Table 1.2 shows the result of the **independent t-test**. It is inferred from the table that the significant value of the variables “impact of sensitivity training” and “supportive sensitivity training” is lesser than 0.05. Hence reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis.

Alternate hypothesis: There is a significant difference between the gender with respect to the impact of sensitivity training and supportive sensitivity.

Table 1.3: One Way Anova

	SIGNIFICANT VALUE
A sensitivity trainer is supportive and understanding about the issues and the problems	0.203
HR gave enough time and resources to complete the sensitivity training	0.044
Sensitivity training is conducted at least once in 6 months and I am satisfied with the quality of training	0.355
Sensitivity training met my expectation	0.194
Suggestions given by the trainee have been taken by the trainer	0.128
I felt confident and competent at the end of the training program	0.903

Inference: Table 1.3 shows the result of **one-way ANOVA**. It is inferred from the table that the significant value of the variable “time and resources for sensitivity training” is lesser than 0.05. Hence reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis.

Alternate hypothesis: There is a significant difference among educational qualification with respect to time and resources for sensitivity training.

Table 1.4: Chi-Square Test

	Asymp. Sig.
HR gave enough time and resources to complete the sensitivity training	0.509
Sensitivity training helpful to me	0.500
I felt confident and competent at the end of the training program	0.873

Inference: Table 1.4 shows the result of the **Chi-square**. It is inferred from the table that the significant value of the variable is greater than 0.05. Hence accept the Null hypothesis and reject the Alternate hypothesis.

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the association between Gender and Sensitivity training for the Employees.

CONCLUSION:

Sensitivity training has an impact on employees where it helps them to perform more efficiently in an organization. An employee who takes the sensitivity training will have a positive outcome. Employees who receive sensitivity training become more welcoming and understanding. It improves interpersonal bonds among the employees. Sensitivity training teaches employees how to act positively, which will help all employees by fostering appropriate and appropriate behavioral and emotional behaviors.

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